

Caputo and Caputo-Fabrizio fractional differential masks for images enhancement

Máscaras diferenciales fraccionarias de Caputo y Caputo-Fabrizio para la mejora de imágenes

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Abstract

Image enhancement is one of the most important tasks in the field of image processing. With the help of computer and programming languages many mathematical methods have been implemented to improve the visual quality of an image. One of the most effective methods for this purpose is the histogram equalization. The construction of fractional differential masks for images enhancement has also been proposed. In this paper, we propose a new way of construction of fractional differential mask based on the Caputo and Caputo-Fabrizio derivatives. The effectiveness of the proposed methods have been compared with the histogram equalization method and the multiplication of each pixel of an image by a constant. The experiments results have shown superiority of the proposed methods, with better visual quality and higher gray-level co-occurrence matrix values in four directions.

Key words and phrases: Contrast image enhancement, fractional calculus, fractional differential mask.

Resumen

La mejora de imágenes es una de las tareas más importantes en el campo del procesamiento de imágenes. Con la ayuda de lenguajes informáticos y de programación, se han implementado muchos métodos matemáticos para mejorar la calidad visual de una imagen. Uno de los métodos más eficaces para este propósito es la ecualización del histograma. También se ha propuesto la construcción de máscaras diferenciales fraccionarias para la mejora de imágenes. En este artículo, se propone una nueva forma de construcción de máscara diferencial fraccional basada en las derivadas de Caputo y Caputo-Fabrizio. La eficacia de los métodos propuestos se ha comparado con el método de ecualización del histograma y la

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multiplicación de cada píxel de una imagen por una constante. Los resultados de los experimentos han demostrado la superioridad de los métodos propuestos, con una mejor calidad visual y valores de matriz de co-ocurrencia de nivel de gris más altos en cuatro direcciones.

Palabras y frases clave: Mejora de la imagen de contraste, cálculo fraccional, Máscara diferencial fraccionaria.

1 Introduction

Digital image processing is a set of techniques applied to digital images with the aim of improving their quality using a computer. For years, these type of techniques have been investigated and used in applications for different tasks such as image enhancement, image restoration and image edge detection, among others. For the image enhancement, various methods have been proposed: Histogram Equalization (HE) is one of the best used methods for image enhancement. It provides better quality of images without loss of any information [12]. The multiplication of each pixel of an image by a constant is also one of the effective methods to make image clearer. Recently, many authors have proposed the construction of masks, for image enhancement, based on fractional derivatives [38-47]. A fractional derivative is an integral operator which generalizes the ordinary derivative, such that if the fractional derivative is represented by D^α then, when $\alpha = n$, it coincides with the usual differential operator D^n [5]. Such kind of operators are defined by the help of spaces as:

Definition 1.1. A function $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is said to be absolutely continuous on $[a, b]$, denoted by $f \in AC[a, b]$, if given $\epsilon > 0$ there exists some $\sigma > 0$ such that

$$\sum_{k=1}^n |f(y_k) - f(x_k)| < \epsilon.$$

whenever $\{[x_k, y_k] : k = 1, \dots, n\}$ is a finite collection of mutually disjoint subintervals of $[a, b]$ with

$$\sum_k (y_k - x_k) < \sigma.$$

Definition 1.2. Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $k = 1, 2, \dots, n-1$, the space $AC^n[a, b]$ is defined by

$$AC^n[a, b] := \{f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R} : f^{(k)}(t) \in C[a, b], f^{(n-1)}(t) \in AC[a, b]\}.$$

There are many definitions of fractional derivatives [42-4]. One of the most popular was defined by Gronwald and Letnikov:

Definition 1.3. Let $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$ with $a < b$, $\alpha > 0$, $f \in C^n[a, b]$. The Gronwald-Letnikov (GL) fractional derivative of order α , is given by

$${}^{GL}D_{at}^\alpha f(t) = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{1}{h^\alpha} \sum_{k=0}^{\left[\frac{x-a}{h}\right]} (-1)^k \binom{\alpha}{k} f(t - kh). \quad (1)$$

where $\left[\frac{x-a}{h}\right]$ denotes the integer part of $\frac{x-a}{h}$.

One of the inconveniences of Gronwald-Letnikov derivative is that the class of functions for which this derivative is defined is very narrow. To overcome this inconvenience, Riemann and Liouville proposed the following definition [17]:

Definition 1.4. Let $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$ with $a < b$, $\alpha > 0$, $f \in AC^n[a, b]$. The Riemann-Liouville (*RL*) fractional derivative of order α , is defined by

$${}^{RL}D_{at}^\alpha f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n - \alpha)} \frac{d^n}{dt^n} \int_a^t (t - s)^{n-(\alpha+1)} f(s) ds.$$

Even though the *RL* approach overcomes the drawbacks related the *GL* definition and it has been applied successfully in many areas of engineering, unfortunately, it leads to initial conditions containing the limit values of the *RL* fractional derivative at the lower terminal $t = a$, for example

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow a} \{{}^{RL}D_{at}^{\alpha-1} f(t)\} = b_1, \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow a} \{{}^{RL}D_{at}^{\alpha-2} f(t)\} = b_2, \quad \dots, \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow a} \{{}^{RL}D_{at}^{\alpha-n} f(t)\} = b_n.$$

In spite of the fact that initial value problems with such initial conditions can be successfully solved mathematically, their solutions are practically useless, because there is no known physical interpretation for such types of initial conditions. An alternative solution to this conflict was proposed by M. Caputo [17]:

Definition 1.5. Let $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$ with $a < b$, $\alpha > 0$, $f \in AC^n[a, b]$. The Caputo fractional derivative of order α , is defined by

$${}^C D_{at}^\alpha f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n - \alpha)} \int_a^t (t - s)^{n-(\alpha+1)} f^{(n)}(s) ds. \tag{2}$$

For $0 < \alpha \leq 1$ and $a = 0$, the numerical approximation of (2) takes the form

$${}^C D_{0x}^\alpha u(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1 - \alpha)} \int_0^x (x - \xi)^{-\alpha} u'(\xi) d\xi \approx \frac{1}{\Gamma(1 - \alpha)} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \int_{\frac{kx}{N}}^{\frac{(k+1)x}{N}} (x - \xi)^{-\alpha} u'(\xi_k) d\xi. \tag{3}$$

To describe material heterogeneity and structures with different scales which cannot be well described by classical local theories or by fractional models with singular kernel, Caputo and Fabrizio introduced a new fractional approach [7]:

Definition 1.6. Let $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$ with $a < b$, $0 < \alpha < 1$, $f \in AC^1[a, b]$. The Caputo-Fabrizio fractional derivative of order α , is defined by

$${}^{CF} D_{ax}^\alpha u(x) = \frac{M(\alpha)}{1 - \alpha} \int_a^x e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}(x-s)} u'(s) ds,$$

where $M(\alpha)$ is a function such that $M(0) = M(1) = 1$.

In [24], Losada and Nieto, suggested the following particular case

$$\begin{aligned} {}^{CF} D_{ax}^\alpha u(x) &= \frac{1}{1 - \alpha} \int_a^x e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}(x-s)} u'(s) ds \\ &= \frac{1}{1 - \alpha} \left(u(x) - e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}x} u(a) \right) - \frac{\alpha}{(1 - \alpha)^2} \int_a^x e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}(x-\tau)} u(\tau) d\tau. \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Taking $a = 0$, formula (4) can be approximated as

$${}^{CF}D_{0x}^{\alpha}u(x) = \frac{1}{1-\alpha} \int_0^x e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}(x-\xi)} u'(\xi) d\xi \approx \frac{1}{1-\alpha} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \int_{\frac{kx}{N}}^{\frac{(k+1)x}{N}} e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}(x-\xi)} u'(\xi_k) d\xi. \quad (5)$$

Fractional derivatives provide interesting possibilities for scientific fields such as anomalous diffusion [40-23], circuit theory [3-43], image processing [33-26] and many others [1-29]. The purpose of this paper is to improve the visual quality of dark images by using Fractional Differential Masks in Caputo (FDMC) and Caputo-Fabrizio (FDMCF) senses. The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: in section 2, we construct a fractional differential mask in the Caputo sense, next, fractional differential mask in Caputo-Fabrizio sense is given in section 3. Section 4 presents the experimental results of the proposed methods. A conclusion is considered in section 5.

2 Prewitt fractional filter in the Caputo sense

The goal of this section is to construct a fractional differential mask based on the Caputo derivative definition. For this purpose, we first discretize numerically the Caputo derivative based on the forward finite difference scheme in the interval $[0, x]$ (analogously $[0, y]$). Let's take a partition of N nodes of the interval $[0, x]$, with step $\Delta x = \frac{x}{N}$. Thus, there are $N + 1$ nodes. The $N + 1$ causal pixels can be given by

$$\begin{cases} u_0 = u(0) \\ u_1 = u(\frac{x}{N}) \\ \vdots \\ u_k = u(\frac{kx}{N}) \\ \vdots \\ u_N = u(x), \end{cases}$$

For $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, by approximating, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\frac{kx}{N}}^{\frac{(k+1)x}{N}} (x-\xi)^{-\alpha} u'(\xi_k) d\xi &\approx \frac{u(\frac{kx+x}{N}) - u(\frac{kx}{N})}{\Delta x} \int_{\frac{kx}{N}}^{\frac{kx+x}{N}} (x-\xi)^{-\alpha} d\xi \\ &= \frac{u(\frac{kx+x}{N}) - u(\frac{kx}{N})}{-(1-\alpha)(\Delta x)^{\alpha}} [(N-k-1)^{1-\alpha} - (N-k)^{1-\alpha}]. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Then, taking (6) into (3), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 {}^C D_{0x}^\alpha u(x) &\approx \frac{1}{(\Delta x)^\alpha \Gamma(2-\alpha)} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \left\{ \left[u\left(\frac{(k+1)x}{N}\right) - u\left(\frac{kx}{N}\right) \right] [(N-k-1)^{1-\alpha} - (N-k)^{1-\alpha}] \right\} \\
 &= \frac{1}{(\Delta x)^\alpha \Gamma(2-\alpha)} \left\{ \begin{aligned} &1^{1-\alpha} u_N + (2^{1-\alpha} - 2 \cdot 1^{1-\alpha}) u_{N-1} \\ &+ (2 \cdot 2^{1-\alpha} - 3^{1-\alpha} - 1^{1-\alpha}) u_{N-2} \\ &+ [(N-j-1)^{1-\alpha} + (N-j+1)^{1-\alpha} \\ &- 2(N-j)^{1-\alpha}] u_j + \dots + [(N-2)^{1-\alpha} \\ &- 2(N-1)^{1-\alpha} + N^{1-\alpha}] u_1 \\ &+ [(N-1)^{1-\alpha} - N^{1-\alpha}] u_0 \end{aligned} \right\}. \tag{7}
 \end{aligned}$$

The anterior approximate difference of fractional partial differential on x and y coordinates are expressed as

$${}^C D_{0x}^\alpha u(x, y) \approx \frac{1}{(\Delta x)^\alpha \Gamma(2-\alpha)} \left\{ \begin{aligned} &1^{1-\alpha} u(x, y) + (2^{1-\alpha} - 2 \cdot 1^{1-\alpha}) u(x-1, y) \\ &+ (2 \cdot 2^{1-\alpha} - 3^{1-\alpha} - 1^{1-\alpha}) u(x-2, y) \\ &+ \dots + [(N-1)^{1-\alpha} - N^{1-\alpha}] u(x-n, y) \end{aligned} \right\}, \tag{8}$$

and

$${}^C D_{0y}^\alpha u(x, y) \approx \frac{1}{(\Delta x)^\alpha \Gamma(2-\alpha)} \left\{ \begin{aligned} &1^{1-\alpha} u(x, y) + (2^{1-\alpha} - 2 \cdot 1^{1-\alpha}) u(x, y-1) \\ &+ (2 \cdot 2^{1-\alpha} - 3^{1-\alpha} - 1^{1-\alpha}) u(x, y-2) \\ &+ \dots + [(N-1)^{1-\alpha} - N^{1-\alpha}] u(x, y-n) \end{aligned} \right\}. \tag{9}$$

As in a digital 2- D gray image $u(x, y)$, the shortest distance on x and y coordinates is one pixel, then we put $\Delta x = \Delta y = 1$, and from (7), we obtain $N + 1$ coefficients c_i ($i = 0, \dots, N$), which

depend on the fractional order α :

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} c_0 = \frac{1^{1-\alpha}}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)}, \\ c_1 = \frac{2^{1-\alpha} - 2 \cdot 1^{1-\alpha}}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)}, \\ c_2 = \frac{2 \cdot 2^{1-\alpha} - 3^{1-\alpha} - 1^{1-\alpha}}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)}, \\ \vdots \\ c_j = \frac{(N-j-1)^{1-\alpha} + (N-j+1)^{1-\alpha} - 2(N-j)^{1-\alpha}}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)}, \\ \vdots \\ c_N = \frac{(N-1)^{1-\alpha} - N^{1-\alpha}}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)}. \end{array} \right.$$

3 Prewitt fractional filter in the Caputo-Fabrizio sense

Following the idea as in the previous section, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\frac{kx}{N}}^{\frac{(k+1)x}{N}} e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}(x-\xi)} u'(\xi_k) d\xi &\approx \frac{u\left(\frac{kx+x}{N}\right) - u\left(\frac{kx}{N}\right)}{\Delta x} \int_{\frac{kx}{N}}^{\frac{kx+x}{N}} e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}(x-\xi)} d\xi, \\ &= \frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha} \cdot \frac{u\left(\frac{kx+x}{N}\right) - u\left(\frac{kx}{N}\right)}{\Delta x} \cdot [e^{-\frac{\alpha(N-k-1)\Delta x}{1-\alpha}} - e^{-\frac{\alpha(N-k)\Delta x}{1-\alpha}}]. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Inserting (10) into (5), we have

$$\begin{aligned} {}^{CF}D_{0x}^\alpha u(x) &\approx \frac{1}{\alpha} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \left\{ \left[\frac{u\left(\frac{(k+1)x}{N}\right) - u\left(\frac{kx}{N}\right)}{\frac{x}{N}} \right] \left[e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}[N-(k+1)]\frac{x}{N}} - e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}[N-k]\frac{x}{N}} \right] \right\} \\ &= \frac{1}{\alpha \cdot \Delta x} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (1 - e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}\Delta x})u_N + (2e^{-\frac{\alpha\Delta x}{1-\alpha}} - e^{-2\frac{\alpha\Delta x}{1-\alpha}} - 1)u_{N-1} + \\ (2e^{-\frac{2\alpha\Delta x}{1-\alpha}} - e^{-3\frac{\alpha\Delta x}{1-\alpha}} - e^{-\frac{\alpha\Delta x}{1-\alpha}})u_{N-2} + \dots + \\ (2e^{-\frac{\alpha(N-j)\Delta x}{1-\alpha}} - e^{-\frac{\alpha(N-j-1)\Delta x}{1-\alpha}} - e^{-\frac{\alpha(N-j+1)\Delta x}{1-\alpha}})u_j \\ + \dots + (2e^{-\frac{\alpha(N-1)\Delta x}{1-\alpha}} - e^{-\frac{\alpha(N-2)\Delta x}{1-\alpha}} - e^{-\frac{\alpha N\Delta x}{1-\alpha}})u_1 \\ + (2e^{-\frac{\alpha N\Delta x}{1-\alpha}} - e^{-\frac{\alpha(N-1)\Delta x}{1-\alpha}} - e^{-\frac{\alpha(N+1)\Delta x}{1-\alpha}})u_0 \end{array} \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

From (11), we obtain $N + 1$ nonzero coefficients c_i ($i = 0, \dots, N$), given by

$$\begin{cases} c_0 = \frac{1}{\alpha\Delta x} (1 - e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}\Delta x}), \\ c_1 = \frac{1}{\alpha\Delta x} (2e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}\Delta x} - e^{-\frac{2\alpha}{1-\alpha}\Delta x} - 1), \\ c_2 = \frac{1}{\alpha\Delta x} (2e^{-2\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}\Delta x} - e^{-3\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}\Delta x} - e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}\Delta x}), \\ \vdots \\ c_j = \frac{1}{\alpha\Delta x} (2e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}(N-j)\Delta x} - e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}(N-j-1)\Delta x} - e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}(N-j+1)\Delta x}), \\ \vdots \\ c_{N-1} = \frac{1}{\alpha\Delta x} (2e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}(N-1)\Delta x} - e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}(N-2)\Delta x} - e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}N\Delta x}), \\ c_N = \frac{1}{\alpha\Delta x} (2e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}N\Delta x} - e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}(N-1)\Delta x} - e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}(N+1)\Delta x}). \end{cases}$$

Taking $\Delta x = \Delta y = 1$, as in the previous section, we obtain the followings two expressions:

$${}^{CF}D_{0y}^\alpha u(x, y) \approx \frac{1}{\alpha} \left\{ \begin{aligned} &(1 - e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}})u(x, y) + (2e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}} - e^{-2\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}} - 1)u(x - 1, y) \\ &+ (2e^{-2\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}} - e^{-3\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}} - e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}})u(x - 2, y) + \dots \\ &+ (2e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}N} - e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}(N-1)} - e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}(N+1)})u(x - n, y) \end{aligned} \right\}, \quad (12)$$

and

$${}^{CF}D_{0y}^\alpha u(x, y) \approx \frac{1}{\alpha} \left\{ \begin{aligned} &(1 - e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}})u(x, y) + (2e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}} - e^{-2\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}} - 1)u(x, y - 1) \\ &+ (2e^{-2\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}} - e^{-3\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}} - e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}})u(x, y - 2) + \dots \\ &+ (2e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}N} - e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}(N-1)} - e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}(N+1)})u(x, y - n) \end{aligned} \right\}. \quad (13)$$

The next images show the results of applying the proposed FDMCF, with different values of differential order α , on the following images: goldhill image, drak bedroom and dark room.

(a) Original image

(f) $\alpha = 0.0075$

Figure 1: Result of applying the proposed FDMCF on goldhill image with different values of differential order α .

Figure 2: Result of applying the proposed FDMCF on a dark bedroom image with different values of differential order α .

(a) Original image

(f) $\alpha = 0.007$

Figure 3: Result of applying the proposed FDMCF on a dark room image with different values of differential order α .

The next tables show the results of contrast in terms of the Gray-Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM) in 4 directions, on the following images: goldhill image, drak bedroom and dark room.

		Angle			
		0 ⁰	45 ⁰	90 ⁰	135 ⁰
Original image		0.2743	0.5685	0.4336	0.5542
M e t h o d	HE	0.5018	0.9403	0.6727	0.9352
	MPIT	0.4642	0.8428	0.6060	0.8476
	FDMC for $\alpha = 0.0155$	7.4922	11.7211	8.8573	11.5499
	FDMC for $\alpha = 0.0165$	13.0910	18.5857	12.7200	18.6007
	FDMC for $\alpha = 0.0170$	15.1278	20.5889	13.4156	20.7000
	FDMCF for $\alpha = 0.0071$	9.0089	12.3465	8.7710	12.4288
	FDMCF for $\alpha = 0.0072$	9.5492	12.8873	9.0874	13.0488
	FDMCF for $\alpha = 0.0073$	9.9501	13.2338	9.2318	13.4732

Table 1: Gold-hill image.

		Angle			
		0 ⁰	45 ⁰	90 ⁰	135 ⁰
Original image		0.0007	0.0888	0.0885	0.0888
M e t h o d	HE	0.2229	0.3526	0.2241	0.3632
	MPITH	0.1345	0.2625	0.1488	0.2638
	FDMC for $\alpha = 0.013$	0.7667	1.4983	1.0776	1.5015
	FDMC for $\alpha = 0.014$	0.7653	1.4477	1.0253	1.4494
	FDMC for $\alpha = 0.015$	0.7172	1.4236	1.0371	1.4240
	FDMCF for $\alpha = 0.005$	0.6574	1.0510	0.6768	1.0653
	FDMCF for $\alpha = 0.006$	0.6459	0.9865	0.6296	0.9923
	FDMCF for $\alpha = 0.007$	0.5014	0.7176	0.4438	0.7180

Table 2: Dark bedroom.

		Angle			
		0 ⁰	45 ⁰	90 ⁰	135 ⁰
Original image		0.4711	0.6691	0.2139	0.6694
M e t h o d	HE	0.6178	0.8568	0.5153	0.8977
	MPITH	0.4221	0.7419	0.4225	0.7560
	FDMC for $\alpha = 0.013$	3.5218	5.4161	3.4127	5.4255
	FDMC for $\alpha = 0.014$	3.6872	5.8437	3.7464	5.8422
	FDMC for $\alpha = 0.015$	3.8128	6.0092	3.8800	6.0260
	FDMCF for $\alpha = 0.005$	2.4504	3.9630	2.6457	3.9593
	FDMCF for $\alpha = 0.006$	2.5697	4.2178	2.8633	4.1469
	FDMCF for $\alpha = 0.007$	2.7114	4.0842	2.6762	4.0415

Table 3: Dark room.

The following images show the comparison of contrast enhancement capability between the methods: MPIT; MPITH; HE; FDMC; and FDMCF applied to the *Goldhill image*.

(a) Original image

(b) MPIT

(c) MPITH

(d) HE

(f) FDMCF with $\alpha = 0.0072$

Figure 4: Comparison of contrast enhancement capability between methods.

The next images show the comparison of contrast enhancement capability between the methods: MPIT; MPITH; HE; FDMC; and FDMCF applied to the *Dark Bedroom image*.

Figure 5: Comparison of contrast enhancement capability between methods.

The next images show the comparison of contrast enhancement capability between the methods: MPIT; MPITH; HE; FDMC; and FDMCF applied to the *Dark room image*.

(a) Original image

(b) MPIT

(c) MPITH

(d) HE

(f) FDMCF with $\alpha = 0.005$

Figure 6: Comparison of contrast enhancement capability between methods.

(a) Dark bedroom image

(b) Dark room image

(c) Gold-hill image

Figure 7: Original images used in the experimental result.

4 Experimental results

The aim of this section is to demonstrate that fractional differential masks based on Caputo (FDMC) and Caputo-Fabrizio (FDMCF) definitions have better capability in texture-enhancing than the traditional approaches for texture-rich image. To this purpose, we analyze the texture-enhancing capability of the proposed masks and discuss the relationship between fractional power parameter α and texture-enhancing details by using Gray-Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM). Finally, we discuss the capability of texture enhancement of the proposed masks by making comparison with Histogram Equalization (HE), Multiplication of each Pixel of an Image by Two (MPIT) and Multiplication of each Pixel of an Image by Three (MPITH) methods. Three images

used in the experimental results are shown in Figures 7. First is dark bedroom image, second is a dark room image, the third one is the gold-hill image. To obtain the fractional differential on the eight symmetric directions and make the fractional differential masks have anti-rotation capability, eight fractional differential masks which are respectively on the directions of 0^0 , 45^0 , 90^0 , 135^0 , 180^0 , 225^0 , 270^0 and 315^0 are implemented in Fig. 8. Considering

$$sum = \frac{c_0 + c_1 + c_2 + \dots + c_n}{8}$$

and taking into account the eight neighboring pixels of a given one, we propose the fractional differential mask, given by Table 4.

C_n	0	0	C_n	0	0	C_n
0	\ddots	0	\vdots	0	\ddots	0
\vdots	0	C_1	C_1	C_1	0	\vdots
C_n	\dots	C_1	sum	C_1	\dots	C_n
\vdots	0	C_1	C_1	C_1	0	\vdots
0	\ddots	0	\vdots	0	\ddots	0
C_n	0	0	C_n	0	0	C_n

Table 4: Fractional differential mask.

For the implementation of the FDMCF method, we have taken only the following three coefficients:

$$c_0 = \frac{1}{\alpha} (1 - e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}}),$$

$$c_1 = \frac{1}{\alpha} (2e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}} - e^{-\frac{2\alpha}{1-\alpha}} - 1),$$

$$c_2 = \frac{1}{\alpha} (2e^{-\frac{2\alpha}{1-\alpha}} - e^{-\frac{3\alpha}{1-\alpha}} - e^{-\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}}),$$

while for the FDMC method, we considered the coefficients:

$$c_0 = \frac{1^{1-\alpha}}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)}, \quad c_1 = \frac{2^{1-\alpha} - 2 \cdot 1^{1-\alpha}}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)}, \quad c_2 = \frac{2 \cdot 2^{1-\alpha} - 3^{1-\alpha} - 1^{1-\alpha}}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)},$$

c_0	0	...							
0	c_1	0	...						
\vdots	0	c_2	0						
	\vdots	0	\ddots	\ddots					
		\vdots	0	c_k	0	\vdots			
			\vdots	\ddots	\ddots	0	...		
				...	0	c_{N-2}	0	\vdots	
					...	0	c_{N-1}	0	
						...	0	c_N	

Mask in the direction of 315^0

					...	0	c_{N-1}	c_N	
				...	0	c_{N-2}	0	\vdots	
				\ddots	\ddots	0	\vdots		
				...	0	c_k	0	...	
			\vdots	0	\ddots	\ddots	\ddots		
			\vdots	0	c_2	0	...		
			0	c_1	0	...			
c_0	0	...							

Mask in the direction of 45^0

		...	0	c_N	0	...			
		...	0	c_{N-1}	0	...			
		...	0	c_{N-2}	0	...			
			\vdots	\vdots	\vdots				
		...	0	c_k	0	...			
			\vdots	\vdots	\vdots				
		...	0	c_2	0	...			
		...	0	c_1	0	...			
		...	0	c_0	0	...			

Mask in the direction of 90^0

		...	0	c_0	0	...			
		...	0	c_1	0	...			
		...	0	c_2	0	...			
			\vdots	\vdots	\vdots				
		...	0	c_k	0	...			
			\vdots	\vdots	\vdots				
		...	0	c_{N-2}	0	...			
		...	0	c_{N-1}	0	...			
		...	0	c_N	0	...			

Mask in the direction of 270^0

\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots
0	0	0	...	0	...	0	0	0	0
c_N	c_{N-1}	c_{N-2}	...	c_k	...	c_2	c_1	c_0	
0	0	0	...	0	...	0	0	0	0
\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots

Mask in the direction of 180^0

\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots						
0	0	0	...	0	...	0	0	0	0
c_0	c_1	c_2	...	c_k	...	c_{N-2}	c_{N-1}	c_N	
0	0	0	...	0	...	0	0	0	0
\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots						

Mask in the direction of 0^0

c_N	0	...							
0	c_{N-1}	0	...						
\vdots	0	c_{N-2}	0						
	\vdots	0	\ddots	\ddots					
		\vdots	0	c_k	0	\vdots			
			\vdots	\ddots	\ddots	0	...		
				...	0	c_2	0	\vdots	
					...	0	c_1	0	
						...	0	c_0	

Mask in the direction of 135^0

					...	0	c_0		
					...	0	c_1	0	
				...	0	c_2	0	\vdots	
				\ddots	\ddots	0	\vdots		
				...	0	c_k	0	...	
			\vdots	0	\ddots	\ddots	\ddots		
			\vdots	0	c_{N-2}	0	...		
			0	c_{N-1}	0	...			
c_N	0	...							

Mask in the direction of 225^0

Figure 8: Different mask

Images a) of the Figures 1, 2 and 3 are the original images while images b), c), d) and f) of Figures 1, 2 and 3 are the results of applying the FDMCF method on the original images with different values of differential order. Images a), b), c), d) and f) of the Figures 4, 5 and 6 are the original image, enhancing result of a) by MPIT, enhancing result of a) by MPITH, enhancing result of a) by HE, enhancing result of a) by FDMC and enhancing result of a) by FDMCF, respectively. On these figures, we can see that images obtained by the proposed methods look better than those obtained by other methods. For the comparison purpose, we use the contrast of Gray-Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM) in four directions. Tables 1, 2 and 3 are the contrasts of GLCM in four directions. From these tables we can conclude that the proposed methods outperform HE, MPIT and MPITH methods. Based on the results shown in Figures 4, 5 and 6 we can see that the proposed methods are more effective than the HE, MPIT and MPITH methods, since they enhance better the visual appearance of an image and make it clearer.

5 Conclusion

In this paper, we proposed construction of fractional differential masks using Caputo and Caputo-Fabrizio fractional derivatives. Experiments results showed that filtered images by the proposed methods have better visual appearance. Moreover, the proposed techniques have demonstrated a good performance with higher GLCM values.

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